

A facile spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper(II) using variamine blue as a chromogenic reagent

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Manuscript received 23 September 2002, revised 20 February 2003, accepted 2 April 2003

A rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of trace amounts of copper using variamine blue (VB) as a chromogenic reagent. The method is based on the reaction of copper with potassium iodide in acidic medium to liberate iodine, which oxidizes VB to a violet coloured species having λ_{\max} at 556 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 2–14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cu. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $4.31 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.48 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The method has been successfully applied to the determination of copper in alloys and synthetic mixtures.

Many spectrophotometric methods for the determination of copper have been reported with some chromogenic reagents, such as 3,3-(1,3-propanediyldiimine)-bis(3-methyl-2-butenone)dioxime¹, 2,2-biquinolyl², cupron³, thiophene-2-aldehydethiosemicarbazone⁴, 4-vanillidinamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole⁵, dimethylglyoxime⁶, cyclohexanethiosemicarbazone⁷ and *n*-phenylglycine⁸.

In the present investigation, variamine blue (VB) has been used as a selective, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of copper. The method has been successfully employed to the determination of copper in alloys and the results are compared with bicyclohexanone oxalyldihydrazone⁹ method.

Results and discussion

The reaction of Cu with KI in acidic medium liberates iodine which forms a violet coloured species instantaneously at the room temperature with VB having at λ_{\max} 556 nm, where the reagent blank shows negligible absorbance.

Effect of iodide concentration and acidity :

The effect of iodide concentration and acidity on the colour development was studied with 14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper. The oxidation of iodide to iodine by copper was effective in the pH range 1.0–1.5, which could be maintained by adding 1 ml of 2 M HCl in the final volume of 10 ml. The liberation of iodine from potassium iodide in an acidic medium was quantitative. However the concentration of HCl should be maintained at the 1.0–1.2 ml ranges. It was found that 1 ml of each 2% potassium iodide and 2 M HCl were sufficient for the liberation of iodine from iodide by copper and subsequent oxidation of VB for complete colour deve-

lopment.

Effect of reagent concentration :

Constant and maximum absorbance values were obtained in the pH range 4.0–5.0. This could be achieved by the addition of 2 ml of 1 M sodium acetate solution in a total volume of 10 ml. An increase in the pH value above 5 affected the stability of the coloured species, whereas colour development did not take place below pH 4. The optimum concentration of VB leading to the maximum colour stability was found to be 0.5 ml of 0.05% reagent per 10 ml of the reaction mixture. 2 ml 1 M sodium acetate solution was found to be sufficient for complete and maximum colour development. Under the optimum reaction conditions, the colour system was stable for a period of 45 min.

Analytical data :

The adherence to Beer's law was studied by measuring the absorbance values of solutions varying copper concentrations. A straight line graph was obtained by plotting absorbance against the concentration of copper. Beer's law was obeyed upto 14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper were found to be $4.31 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.48 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The results obtained for potassium iodide and VB showed that relative error did not exceed $\pm 1\%$.

The determination of Cu^{II} from copper sulfate solution (Table 3) shows that accurate and consistently reproducible are obtainable with relative errors $\leq 0.4\%$ and standard deviations $\leq 0.04 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

Effect of diverse ion :

The effect of various diverse ions at 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ levels on

Table 1. Determination of copper(II) in alloys

Sample	% of Copper found (bicyclohexanone oxalyldihydrazone method)	% of Copper found*	Relative error %
German silver	71.28	71.23	-0.08
Bronze	80.79	80.70	-0.11
Brass	67.64	67.70	0.08
Aluminium bronze	77.32	77.20	-0.16
Gun metal	84.96	85.10	0.16

*Average of five determinations.

Table 2. Determination of copper(II) in synthetic mixtures

Metal ions	Compositions $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Copper found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Relative error %
Cu + Mo	4.1 + 3.0	4.101	0.02
Cu + Ba	4.0 + 3.5	3.996	-0.10
Cu + Mg	5.5 + 2.0	5.504	+0.07
Cu + U	5.0 + 2.5	4.998	-0.04

*Average of five determinations.

Table 3. Determination of copper(II) in copper sulfate solution

Copper taken $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Copper found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Standard deviation $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Recovery %
2.55	2.56	0.01	100.39
5.10	5.08	0.01	99.61
10.20	10.18	0.02	99.80
15.30	15.36	0.03	100.39
20.40	20.41	0.04	100.05

*Average of five determinations.

the determination of copper was examined. An error of $\pm 3\%$ in absorbance reading was considered tolerable. The tolerance limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of various foreign ions were found to be as follows. Bromide (300), nitrate (200), chloride, acetate, borate (150), Fe^{III} (masked), Co^{II} , V^{IV} , W^{VI} , U^{VI} , phosphate, sulfate (100), Ni^{II} , In^{III} (75), Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ba^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Mo^{VI} (50), Zn^{II} , Mg^{II} (25). Various oxidants such as CrO_4^{2-} , Fe^{3+} , Ce^{4+} , IO_3^- , and some reducing agents are found to interfere. However, some of these ions could be masked by the addition of an appropriate amount of EDTA solution. Fe^{3+} can be masked using sodium fluoride.

Application :

The developed method was applied to the quantitative determination of traces of copper in different alloy samples. The results of the analysis of the above alloy samples (Table 1) compared favorable with those from a reference method⁹. Also various synthetic mixtures of copper with Mo, Ba, Mg

and U metal ions were prepared and the amount of copper present was determined by the proposed method (Table 1). The precision of the proposed method was evaluated by a replicate analysis of samples containing copper in different concentrations.

Experimental

A Secomam Anthelie NUA022 UV-visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell and a WTW pH 330 pH meter were used. All the reagents used were A.R. grade and double-distilled water was used throughout.

Standard stock solution (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of copper was prepared in water and standardized by the bicyclohexanone oxalyldihydrazone method. A 0.05% variamine blue (E. Merck) solution was prepared in methanol-water (1 : 4). A 2% aq. KI solution and 2 M HCl and 1 M sodium acetate were prepared.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing 2–14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper, 2% KI (1 ml) and 2 M HCl (1 ml) were added. The mixture was gently shaken till the appearance of yellow colour, indicating the liberation of iodine. Then, 0.5 ml of 0.05% VB was added, followed by 1 M sodium acetate solution (2 ml). The contents were diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the coloured solutions were measured at 556 nm against the reagent blank.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Microtron Center of Mangalore University for technical help.

References

1. S. Karabocek, S. Nohut, O. Dalman and S. Gunner, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2000, **408**, 163.
2. H. Diehl and G. F. Smith, "The Copper Reagents : Cuproin Neocuproin, Bathocuproin", Frederick Smith Chemical Co., Columbus, 1958.
3. N. Rajput, V. Kadam and S. Devi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 88.
4. J. A. Munozleyva, J. M. Cano Pavon and F. Pino, *An. Quim.*, 1973, **69**, 251.
5. R. A. Nazarath, B. Narayana and N. V. Sreekumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1016.
6. U. Muralikrishna and A. Shivaramakrishna, *Asian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **13**, 289.
7. G. Gonestar, F. G. Sanchez, D. P. Bendito and M. Valcarcel, *An. Quim.*, 1978, **74**, 1522.
8. Nelson De Araujo, *Eclition Quim.*, 1988, **13**, 101.
9. A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 4th. ed., ELBS, Longman, 1978.